

EVALUATION OF THE VOLUNTARY PREPARATORY SCHOOL OF ENGLISH THROUGH THE EYES OF STUDENTS:

A CASE STUDY AT A STATE UNIVERSITY IN TÜRKİYE: THE VOLUNTARY ENGLISH PREPARATORY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This study examines students' perceptions of the effectiveness of intensive English classes offered by the voluntary English preparatory school of a state university in Türkiye, using the Context-Input-Process-Product (CIPP) program evaluation model. A mixed-methods approach was employed, with quantitative data collected via a previously validated questionnaire and qualitative data gathered through open-ended questions. Eighty-four preparatory students, all of whom had studied at the school in previous academic years, participated. Quantitative data were analysed using SPSS 21 and interpreted through descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were examined using content analysis. Findings from both data sets were consistent. Results indicated that students were dissatisfied with the physical conditions of the school and with the program in terms of speaking skills, although they expressed satisfaction with their teachers. Based on these findings, it is concluded that greater emphasis should be placed on developing listening and speaking skills, and that improvements are needed in the school's physical environment.

Keywords: Case Study, Program Evaluation, Voluntary Preparatory School of English, CIPP Model.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Evaluation is a natural part of our lives since as human beings; we evaluate every day. From practitioners and managers, to policymakers, we all make judgements regarding students, clients, personnel, programs, and policies (Stufflebeam, 2003). These judgements lead us to make choices and decisions, that is, whether to change our choices and decisions or to make adaptations for the purpose of improvement. In that view, evaluation of our programs becomes inevitable if we desire to have a more effective one. Additionally, the aim of program evaluation is to give feedback through the improvement, accountability and enlightenment aspects to ensure that programs effectively meet their objectives and serve the needs of their clients. To address those aims, numerous studies on the evaluation of language programs have been conducted (Erdoğan, 2005; Güllü, 2007; Uzunboylu & Hürsen, 2008; Hişmanoğlu, 2012; Coşkun, 2013). In other words, recent studies have increasingly focused on the program evaluation of the preparatory schools of some universities (Özüdoğru, 2017). To give an example, Coşkun and Daloğlu (2010) studied English Language Teacher Education program using Peacock's model. Similarly, Yavuz and Zehir-Topkaya (2013) investigated the perspectives of Turkish educators about the changes made in English Language Teacher Education program released by Turkish Higher Education Council (HEC) in 2006. Karakaş (2012) focused on the evaluation of English Language Teacher Education Program in Türkiye as well. Coşaner (2013) studied the reflections of freshman students on preparatory school program. On the other hand, Özüdoğru (2017) evaluated the voluntary English preparatory program of a Turkish university. Similarly, İnal & Aksoy (2014) conducted research on the evaluation of the preparatory school curriculum of Çankaya University. In addition, by utilizing CIPP program evaluation model, Yılmaz-Vırlan (2014) carried out a study on the effectiveness of the program of a public university in terms of its speaking curriculum. Özkanal and Hakan (2010) also studied whether the English preparatory programs were effective or not. Sert and Dağdeviren (2013) investigated English preparatory education from pre-service teachers' perspectives. Employing CIPP model, Akpur et al. (2016) evaluated the curriculum of English preparatory at a state university in Türkiye. Furthermore, Tunç (2010) developed a questionnaire and evaluated the effectiveness of the preparatory school program of a state university in Türkiye with the help of CIPP program evaluation.

With regard to program evaluation, numerous evaluation models exist in the current literature, one of which is *the CIPP Model*. The CIPP model was developed by Stufflebeam in the late 1960s to support improvement and ensure accountability for federally funded U.S. public school initiatives, particularly those focused on enhancing teaching and learning in inner-city school districts. This model is widely used for evaluating the context, input, process, output of programs. It offers a comprehensive framework for conducting both formative and summative evaluations of programs, projects, personnel, products, organizations, policies, and evaluation systems. According to the principle of this model, the evaluation should give decision-makers, administrators, teachers, policy makers, and stakeholders appropriate information (Stufflebeam, 2005). The model was

developed against the classic evaluation, which employs “*standardized achievement tests*” and “*peer or expert review*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 310) via experimental design and objective-based evaluation. The CIPP model does not try to prove, but it tries to improve the program. In other words, the model tries to find out the factors which has an influence on success and failure in the program. According to the model, “*the society and its agents cannot make their programs unless they learn where they are weak or strong*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 62). The model assesses the context, input, process, and product of programs. C stands for context, I stands for input, P stands for process, and P stands for product.

Firstly, context evaluation, that is the evaluation of setting, is generally associated with needs assessment. “*In context evaluation, evaluators assess needs, problems, assets, and opportunities, plus relevant contextual conditions and Dynamics*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 312). It asks, ‘What needs to be done?’ When referring to needs assessment, it encompasses both the needs of students and those of the community. The key components of context evaluation are considered to be the relevant context, the target population and its needs, the identification of the opportunities that address these needs. With the help of context evaluation, decision makers can “*define goals and set priorities*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 312), and they can make sure that “*program goals are targeted to address significant, assessed needs and problems*” (Stufflebeam, p. 312). Thanks to context evaluation, evaluators can “*judge whether the program was guided by appropriate goals*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 312), and they can “*judge whether the outcomes of the program were responsiveness to its targeted needs, problems, and goals*” (Stufflebeam, 2005, p. 312). Therefore, context evaluation helps us determine the goals which is appropriate for the environment.

Secondly, with the evaluation of the input in the CIPP model, it is expected to find out how to address the identified needs. That is, it is targeted “*to determine which resources are available, which strategies are considered for the program, and which plan is best to meet the requirements in order to guide the design of the process in the program.*” (Turan, 2017). Furthermore, the goals, instructional strategies, the learners, the teachers, the content, and all the materials needed are all the ingredients of input evaluation, where the evaluator identifies and assesses other approaches and plans in order to meet the defined needs and goals. It asks, “How should it be done?” in order to identify the strategies that will help reach the desired goals. That is, it aims to meet the identified needs.

Thirdly, the process evaluation finds out solutions to those involved in how the program could be implemented better, the points which obstacle to achieve the program, and the necessary components recognized. It asks, “Is it being done?” In this regard, one of the objectives of the process evaluation is to give feedback to staff and managers. Process evaluation gives us an opportunity to check whether the program is being implemented well or not. “*Important objectives of process evaluation include documenting the process and providing feedback regarding (a) the extent to which the planned activities are carried out and (b) whether adjustments or revisions of the plan are necessary*” (Zhang, et al., 2011. p. 65). Process evaluation is useful for service

learning projects since “(a) it provides information to make on-site adjustments to the projects, and (b) it fosters the development of relationships between the evaluators (in this case, the two task force members in research and evaluation methodology) and the clients/stakeholders that are based on a growing collaborative understanding and professional skill competencies, which can promote the project’s long-term sustainability” (Zhang, et al., 2011. p. 65).

Finally, the outcomes of a program are assessed with the help of product evaluation. It asks, “Did the program succeed?” “*The purpose of a product evaluation is to measure, interpret, and judge a project’s outcomes by assessing their merit, worth, significance, and probity. Its main purpose is to ascertain the extent to which the needs of all the participants were met.*” (Zhang, et al., 2011. p. 66). Stufflebeam and Coryn (2007) propose that a combination of techniques should be employed, which will help cross-check the various findings, so that a comprehensive set of outcomes can be assessed. Therefore, a wide range of techniques, including logs and diaries of outcomes, interviews of beneficiaries and other stakeholders, case studies, hearings, focus groups, document/records retrieval and analysis, analysis of photographic records, achievement tests, rating scales, trend analysis of longitudinal data, longitudinal or cross-sectional cohort comparisons, and comparison of project costs and outcomes, can be used in product evaluations.

Consequently, the CIPP model is based on “*an objectivist quest for clear, unambiguous answers. It subscribes to the values of free, democratic society. It stresses that evaluation’s most important purpose is not only to prove but also to improve. It provides for equitable, meaningful engagement of stakeholders in the evaluation process.*” (Stufflebeam, p. 336). This model is applicable for both formative use in developing and conducting programs and summative use in judging completed programs and meeting accountability requirements. It is applicable for “*a wide range of users, including evaluators, program specialists, researchers, developers, policy groups, leaders, administrators, committees or task groups, and laypersons*” (Stufflebeam, p. 310). It is an ongoing evaluation practice which “*is based on learning by doing*” (Stufflebeam, p. 310). In other words, it always tries to find out the mistakes in evaluation practice and correct them and so that the evaluator will develop approaches for new procedures, and effective evaluation will be accomplished. Considering the advantages mentioned so far, the CIPP evaluation model was preferred for the case of this study.

It has been more three years since the Voluntary Preparatory English Program started to be offered to the first-year students at participating university. Since the beginning of the program, every academic year, there have been some changes in the program including syllabus, materials, weekly schedule, and physical conditions. However, these changes have been done without considering students’ needs and opinions about the program. In this regard, with the help of the CIPP evaluation model, this research aims to provide stakeholders with valuable insights into students’ beliefs regarding the effectiveness of the voluntary preparatory classes. Besides that, this study is expected be valuable for the instructors of school of foreign languages department of the participating university as well, as they will be able to see the students’ beliefs, and so that they will

be able to develop their lesson plans and materials in the following academic years regarding those beliefs. Consequently, it is expected that showing the beliefs of the students will be beneficial not only for the students and the instructors, but also for the school of foreign languages department of the participating university itself for the selection of right materials, developing a better and applicable syllabus in the following academic years. To achieve the objectives of the current study, this research seeks address the following research questions:

- 1) What are the students' overall perceptions of the emphasis on four skills, grammar and vocabulary learning in the prep classes in relation to their current level of English proficiency?
- 2) What are the students' opinions about their own competencies in terms of four language skills?
- 3) What are the students' perceptions of the materials, teaching methods, assessment procedures commonly practiced in the program along with the physical conditions and communication facilities?
- 4) Are the students satisfied with the current program and its components?

2. METHODOLOGY

The CIPP model is considered the most suitable framework for application in the context of this research, as the CIPP evaluation model tries to *"help improve and achieve accountability" "for public school projects, especially those keyed to improving teaching and learning in inner-city school districts"* (Stufflebeam, p. 310). It is *"a comprehensive framework for conducting formative and summative evaluation of programs, projects, personnel, products, organizations, policies, and evaluation systems"* (Stufflebeam, p. 309). In this regard, according to the principle of this model, the evaluation should give decision-makers, administrators, teachers, policy makers, and stakeholders appropriate information (Stufflebeam, 2005). In addition, the CIPP model aims not to prove, but to improve the program. To put a finer point on it, the model tries to explore the factors which has a significant impact on the success and failure in the program. The CIPP always tries to find out the mistakes in evaluation practice and correct them, and so that the evaluator will develop approaches for new procedures, and effective evaluation will be accomplished. Therefore, employing this model, the researcher can evaluate the context (i.e. the setting) the input, the process, and the product of the intended program.

2.1. Setting and the Participants

The freshmen students at the participating university are enrolled in an intensive English program through preparatory classes. The program was firstly carried out at the building of the Faculty of Education, then at the building of Vocational Health High School. The program is voluntary, as indicated by its title, rather than mandatory. In other words, every freshmen student who wants to develop their English proficiency can enrol at the preparatory classes and spend a year in this program. The students who are successful in this program can receive a certificate of achievement,

and they are exempt from taking the obligatory English courses given in their departments whereas the students who fail do not retake the preparatory program, but they go on their education in their departments, and they have to take the obligatory English courses given in their departments. Therefore, it was expected to reach as many students as possible who have taken the preparatory of English program in the last two years in order to conduct a valid and reliable research. Namely, the subjects of this research are the students who studied at voluntary preparatory school of English at the participating university in the previous academic years. The reason why the students who are currently studying at voluntary preparatory school of English were not involved in this study is because it was thought that those students may not evaluate the program sincerely, as they haven't completed it yet.

There were 76 students enrolled in the Voluntary Preparatory School of English, 60 of whom participated in this study. Additionally, 35 students were enrolled in the program in a subsequent cohort, with 24 participating in this study. The distribution of participants can be displayed as follows:

Table 1

Demographic distribution of the students

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>18</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>19</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>2,4</i>
<i>20</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Age 21</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>38,1</i>
<i>22</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>23</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>Gender Male</i>	<i>45</i>	<i>53,6</i>
<i>Female</i>	<i>39</i>	<i>46,4</i>
<i>Anatolian</i>	<i>58</i>	<i>69</i>
<i>Science</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>High School Vocational</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>Graduated</i>		
<i>General</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Others</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>2,4</i>
<i>Architecture</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>Molecular Biology and Genetics</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9,5</i>
<i>Sociology</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>4,8</i>
<i>Mechanical Engineering</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>29,8</i>
<i>Business</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>15,5</i>

<i>Departments</i>	<i>Electrical and Electronic Engineering</i>	5	6
	<i>Urban and Regional Planning</i>	4	4,8
	<i>Civil Engineering</i>	11	13,1
	<i>History</i>	2	2,4
	<i>Economics</i>	5	6
	<i>Turkish Literature</i>	3	3,6
Total		84	100

In this context, the Voluntary Preparatory School of English provides its students with 25 hours of instruction per week. Students who want to join this program are required to take a placement test, and they are ranked according to their scores on this placement test. In the first two years, although the students were placed in appropriate classes in terms of their scores on the placement test, the same materials were used in every class without regarding the students' levels of English. For the assessment, students had to take quizzes, midterms and a final exam. The assessment percentages of the program can be displayed as follow:

Table 2

The assessment percentages

<i>Semester</i>	<i>Midterms</i>		<i>Quizes</i>		<i>Profeciency Exams</i>	
	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>First Semester</i>	2	20%	5	10%		
<i>Second Semester</i>	2	20%	5	10%	1	50%

2.2. Instruments

Questionnaires are usually used in the studies of beliefs and practices. (e.g. MacDonald Badger & White, 2001). With the help of questionnaires, a researcher can obtain both quantitative and qualitative data. Therefore, for this research, the questionnaire developed by Tunç (2010) was used for collecting learners' opinions about the effectiveness of the Voluntary Preparatory School of English. The adapted questionnaire contains 54 closed ended items which requires the participating students to respond to statements on four- and five-point scales, along with open-ended questions to obtain more valid and reliable data. The adapted version of the questionnaire was piloted with 30 students, yielding a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.975, indicating a very high level of reliability (Field, 2017). The reliability analysis of the scale can be seen as displayed in Table 3.

<i>Reliability Statistics</i>	
Cronbach's	N of
Alpha	Items
,975	54

Table 3 - Data Collection and Analysis

This study was conducted during the spring term. It marks the third academic year that the students at the participating university have been offered an intensive English program through the Voluntary Preparatory School of English. However, only the students who have completed the program since its beginning were included in this study because they were considered to give more accurate and reliable responses to the statements in the questionnaire. For the quantitative data, a descriptive analysis technique was utilized to make an objective analysis of the gathered data. For the qualitative data, content analysis technique was used in order to support the quantitative results.

2.3. Limitations

This research tried to explore the students' perceptions about the effectiveness of the Voluntary Preparatory School of English with the help of a questionnaire. In addition, it aimed to find out whether the students who have completed the program share common beliefs about the program or not. Therefore, it was difficult to reach all the students, as the intended participating students were already studying in their respected departments. However, with the help of social media groups, such as the Facebook group of the preparatory school of the participating university, which was created for the preparatory students, many of the students who have completed the preparatory of English program were reached. However, the students who don't have any social media accounts or whose contact information couldn't be obtained were not included in this study.

3. FINDINGS

In line with the research questions, the average ratings of all participants are presented below.

RQ1: What are the students' overall perceptions of the emphasis on four skills, grammar and vocabulary learning in the prep classes in relation to their current level of English proficiency?

Table 4

Students' perceptions of the emphasis on four skills, grammar and vocabulary

<i>Skills</i>	<i>Always</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>Rarely</i>	<i>Never</i>
	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Writing</i>	22,6	60,7	16,7		

<i>Reading</i>	39,3	46,4	9,5	4,8	
<i>Listening</i>	45,2	42,9	7,1		4,8
<i>Speaking</i>	51,2	28,6	15,5	4,8	
<i>Grammar</i>	51,2	44	4,8		
<i>Vocabulary</i>	48,8	36,9	14,3		

As is clearly seen from Table 4., according to the participating students, all the language skills were emphasized during their learning procedures in preparatory school; however, they believe that grammar (*Always 51,2% and Often 44%*) and vocabulary (*48,8% and 36,9%*) were the most emphasized skills while they were studying at the Voluntary Preparatory School of English. On the other hand, some of the students think that reading skill (*Rarely 4,8%*), listening skill (*Never 4,8%*), and speaking skill (*Rarely 4,8%*) need to be more emphasized in the class. Some of their views about the emphasis on four skills, grammar and vocabulary are listed below:

“Dilbilgisi eğitimi oldukça başarılı idi ama konuşma etkinliklerinin daha fazla yapılması daha etkili olurdu.”

“Konuşma becerisini geliştirme fırsatımız yeterince olmadı.”

“Teorik olarak yeterli bir eğitim verildiğini düşünüyorum, fakat pratik açıdan ‘konuşma becerisi’ biraz daha yoğunlaştırılabilir.”

RQ2: What are the students’ opinions about their own competencies in terms of four language skills?

Table 5

Students’ opinions about their own competencies in terms of four skills

<i>Skills</i>	<i>Quite competent</i> %	<i>Competent</i> %	<i>Incompetent</i> %	<i>Quite incompetent</i> %
<i>Writing</i>	16,68	52,56	26,76	3,96
<i>Reading</i>	23	42,86	25,6	8,53
<i>Listening</i>	15,96	30,46	33,32	20,24
<i>Speaking</i>	17,26	32,93	33,51	16,28

According to the results displayed in Table 5., most of the participating students feel that they are competent in four skills; however, they feel more competent in reading (*Quite competent 23% and Competent 42,86%*) and writing skills (*Quite competent 16,68% and Competent 52,56%*) whereas they feel less competent in listening (*Quite competent 15,96% and Competent 30,46%*) and speaking skills (*Quite competent 17,26% and Competent 32,93%*). Some of their opinions about their competency are listed below:

“Yabancı dilde dinleme, okuma ve yazmada bana özgüven kazandırdı.”

“Sıfır olan İngilizcemi geliştirdi, okuduğumu daha rahat anlıyorum.”

RQ3: What are the students’ perceptions of the materials, teaching methods, assessment procedures commonly practiced in the program along with the physical conditions and communication facilities?

Table 6

Students’ opinions about the materials

<i>Materials</i>	<i>Quite insufficient</i>	<i>Sufficient</i>	<i>Insufficient</i>	<i>Quite insufficient</i>
	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Reading texts</i>	33,3	42,9	23,8	
<i>Listening CDs/ DVDs</i>	38,1	40,5	14,3	7,1
<i>Writing Materials</i>	32,1	35,7	27,4	4,8
<i>Grammar Materials</i>	40,5	47,6	7,1	4,8
<i>Visaual and Audial Speaking Materials</i>	41,7	36,9	14,3	7,1
<i>Materials related to Daily life</i>	26,2	61,9	4,8	7,1

Regarding Table 6., a great majority of the participating students believe that the materials used in their classes including reading texts (*Quite sufficient 33,3% and Sufficient 42,9%*), listening materials (*Quite sufficient 38,1% and Sufficient 40,5%*), writing materials (*Quite sufficient 32,1% and Sufficient 35,7%*), materials for grammar instruction (*Quite sufficient 40,5% and Sufficient 47,6%*), visual & audio materials (*Quite sufficient 41,7% and 36,9%*), and materials related to daily life use (*Quite sufficient 26,2% and Sufficient 61,9%*) are all thought to be sufficient. However, many of the students believe that the materials used in grammar instruction were more adequate than the other materials provided (*Quite sufficient 40,5% and Sufficient 47,6%*).

Table 7

Students’ opinions about teaching methods

<i>Teaching methods</i>	<i>Always</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>Rarely</i>	<i>Never</i>
	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Students’ asking questions</i>	39,3	51,2	4,8	4,8	
<i>Role play</i>	22,6	23,8	41,7	11,9	
<i>Group work</i>	20,2	23,8	36,9	16,7	2,4
<i>Instructor’s lecturing</i>	41,7	53,6	4,8		

<i>Pair work</i>	23,8	29,8	22,6	19	4,8
<i>Students' question answering</i>	33,3	56	10,7		
<i>Discussion</i>	16,7	39,3	22,6	16,7	4,8
<i>Students' making Presentations</i>	10,7	33,3	20,2	28,6	7,1

The results displayed in Table 7. indicate that “students’ question answering” (*Always 33,3% and Often 56%*), “students’ asking questions” (*Always 39,3% and Often 51,2%*) and “instructors’ lecturing” (*Always 41,7% and Often 53,6%*) were the most dominant methods used in their classes. On the other hand, according to Table 7., the participating students think that “students’ making presentation” was the least used teaching method in their classes.

Table 8

Students' opinions about assessment

<i>Assessment</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly disagree</i>
	%	%	%	%
<i>Exams reflect the content of the course.</i>	45,2	47,6	7,1	
<i>Exams and quizzes help me learn better</i>	58,3	41,7		
<i>The difficulty of exams is generally consistent with each other.</i>	46,4	41,7	11,9	
<i>Portfolio is beneficial to evaluate the improvement of my language skills.</i>	28,6	64,3	7,1	
<i>The number of exams is sufficient.</i>	29,8	53,6	11,9	4,8

According to the findings presented in Table 8., it is obvious that the participating students mostly feel that they were pleased with the assessment regarding all the variables mentioned in the table; however, a greater percentage of them think that the number of the exams were not adequate (*Disagree 11,9% and Strongly disagree 4,8%*).

Table 9*Students' opinions about the educational setting*

<i>Context</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i> %	<i>Agree</i> %	<i>Disagree</i> %	<i>Strongly disagree</i> %
<i>Pleased with the building and classrooms</i>	6,8	20,2	33,7	39,3

It can be clearly seen from Table 9. that more than half of the students were not pleased with the physical conditions of the school including building and classrooms (*Disagree 33,7% and Strongly disagree 39,3%*). Some of their views about the physical conditions are listed below:

“Kendimize ait ydb binası yoktu, sağlık meslek yüksekokulunda ders alıyorduk, en kısa zamanda bina yapılırsa daha sağlıklı olacaktır.”

“Each term training was provided in different service buildings.”

Table 10*Students' opinions about the communication facilities*

<i>Communication facilities</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i> %	<i>Agree</i> %	<i>Disagree</i> %	<i>Strongly disagree</i> %
<i>I can reach my instructors whenever I want.</i>	64,3	26,2	9,5	
<i>When I have a question, I can easily ask my instructors.</i>	69	31		
<i>I can speak up my ideas in class.</i>	57,1	42,9		
<i>Our ideas are taken into account while designing in-class activities.</i>	46,4	48,8	4,8	
<i>I can easily reach the administrators.</i>	38,1	29,8	27,4	4,8

According to the results displayed in Table 10., a great percentage of the students say that they can reach their instructors whenever they want, and when they have a question, they can easily ask their instructors, they can speak up their ideas in class. In addition to these, they mention that while designing in-class activities, their opinions are taken into consideration as well. However, the results also show that the participating students may have difficulty in reaching the administrators (*Disagree 27,4% and Strongly disagree 4,8%*).

RQ4: Are the students satisfied with the current program and its components?**Table 11***Students' general opinions about the program and its components*

<i>Satisfaction with the program and its components</i>	<i>Sufficient %</i>	<i>Insufficient %</i>
<i>Program</i>	<i>95%</i>	<i>5%</i>
<i>Instructors</i>	<i>85%</i>	<i>15%</i>

As is presented in Table 11., it is obvious that a great percentage of the students say that they were satisfied with the program they were provided in the Voluntary Preparatory School of English (*Sufficient 95%*). Likewise, as consistent with the obtained results from the questionnaire items, the participating students also mention that they were pleased with their instructors (*Sufficient 85%*). Some of their opinions about the program and their instructors are listed below:

“Hazırlık eğitimimden memnun kaldım yine olsa yine alırdım.”

“Başarı basamağımın ilk adımı oldu. Almış olduğum eğitimle İngilizce temelimi oluşturdum ve Erasmus’u kazanmamda en büyük etken oldu.”

“Dilbilgisi, okuma, yazma ve kullanılan ders yöntemleriyle verimli bir yıl oldu.”

“Ders programları, ders materyalleri ve konular, öğrencilere dil öğretmek için gayretli ve gerçekten kaliteli hocalarımızla çok güzel bir yıl geçirdim.”

“Hocalarım sürekli iletişim halinde idi. Her konuda yardımcı oldular.”

4. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this research was to investigate the effectiveness of the intensive English classes provided by the Voluntary English Preparatory School through using CIPP program evaluation model. To achieve this aim, a total of 84 students from different cohorts were involved in this study. Mixed method research was employed in order to gather the necessary data, and the collected data was analysed through descriptive statistics and content analysis techniques.

The results showed that regarding *the Context Evaluation*, the participating students were not satisfied with the educational setting. In light of this finding, the results align with those of previous evaluation studies in the literature, such as Tunç (2010).

As for the *Input Evaluation*, the participating students, who are coming from different departments, mentioned that their needs were highly met via the program provided; however, according to

the students, more emphasis should be put on speaking and listening activities. Similarly, İnal & Aksoy (2014), Karataş (2007) and Tunç (2010) reached similar results.

Considering the *Process Evaluation*, the students were pleased with the methods, materials, and assessment; however, they think more communicative activities should be added, which is a similar finding in Tunç's (2010) study. In addition, a great majority of the students were pleased with the communication feasibility, except reaching the administrators. Likewise, Tunç's (2010) study reported comparable findings as well.

With regard to the *Product Evaluation*, the results indicated that the participating students felt themselves competent in language skills and components except listening and speaking, but the results obtained from the qualitative data revealed that the students didn't feel highly competent in speaking. Likewise, similar findings were found in Ulum (2016) study.

As a consequence, the findings of the current study suggest that the program requires some improvements, particularly in relation to the educational environment. Also, the content of the program should be reconsidered, as well, particularly the speaking activities. Having mentioned the necessary points in the evaluation of the program, the administrators and teachers may take these suggestions into account while shaping their program in the following academic year.

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